

Legal Challenges for Chinese Investment in Special Economic Zones in Mexico.

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Abstract

It is a clear fact that from November last year the world changed considerably, however, before a new geopolitics, it is advisable to have new partners and redesign economic policies according to the needs. For this reason, I would like to point out that this article is still an unfinished topic, it is under construction because it is derived from the international situation, what I write below is for comments and suggestions.

On the other hand, Mexico just created Special Economic Zones based on China's experience to receive foreign capital to invest in areas such as aerospace, electricity, automotive and energy sectors. After the blunder regarding the cancellation of the tender train, Mexico to build mutual trust, deeper integration of their interests and promote exchange one by one, also, to exert its influence in the region to promote the relationship between China and Latin America. Moreover, in Guangdong, May 2016, was held the "Mexico-China Cooperation Forum." The forum opened with the signing of 18 cooperation agreements, including projects to promote investment and to facilitate information exchange. Additionally, on the last day of G20 summits, the presidents of the People's Republic of China and Mexico discussed the opportunity to chart a roadmap of bilateral cooperation for the next five years, in which it is envisaged to cooperate in the construction of Special Economic Zones.

Keywords:

Special Economic Zones, Asia-Pacific, China, Mexico, economy, foreign trade, investment, strategic partnership.

Introduction

Since the departure of the United Kingdom from the European Union, the world has not been the same again, adding the result of the United States elections.

Even in universities, it is taught that the country that promotes trade liberalization, globalization and the new economic order is the United States. By contrast, the country with the highest protectionism was China. Who would say the papers are being switched?

Mexico, under that scheme, is still betting to invest most of its economy in the neighbor of the north. Did we imagine NAFTA could turn 360 degrees? Even worst, the possibility of being renegotiated to become a bilateral agreement and not more trilateral.

However, for the sake of being optimistic, we are facing a new conjuncture, a new era and therefore new opportunities.

It is a clear fact that China has grown and now it more than longer an economic phenomenon, it is a reality that no one can deny.

As is well known, Mexico shares a privileged location with China, the Pacific Ocean. Through this favored position since previous years channels have been opened for merchandise trade.

Mexico now urgently needs to diversify its markets and needs to immediately turn to Asia, specifically China.

For this purpose, Mexico in November 2016 enacted a law to create, for the first time, three Special Economic Zones (from now on EEZ's).

The project was presented as a major impetus to alleviate the historical backwardness of southern Mexico. The objective, however, is to offer foreign companies a safe and business-friendly environment through a preferential tax and customs regime. The EEZ's will also offer some additional benefits such as soft loans from

Mexican development banks and strict security measures to ensure the rule of law. As elsewhere, it is assumed that the EEZ's will attract multinational companies to deploy operations in these areas to generate high-paying jobs, boost innovation and exports, and improve Mexico's competitiveness in international markets.

In the world, when the Special Economic Zones have been successful, it has worked as a very powerful tool to reduce poverty and detonate the economic development of regions lagging behind. The successful EEZ's have been those that have been implemented under an integral approach in sites with real productive potential.

The first modern EEZ's was created in Shannon, Ireland, in 1959, but it was from the 1980s that this instrument took on the greater scope with the proliferation of Chinese EEZs, where successful cases such as Shenzhen Three decades achieved per capita GDP growth of more than 150 times.¹

The Special Economic Zones represent a model of success, especially in China, whose country is a pioneer in the creation of these zones. Up until now, in places where the Special Economic Zones have been installed, local trade has been boosted and investment attracted, which automatically becomes more and better jobs, and greater economic output, and therefore a better standard of living.

The EEZ's were created more than 50 years ago and had been denominated as free trade zones, industrial free zone, among others. "The first known Economic Zone was born at Dublin Airport, Ireland and dates from 1959; However, it is until the middle of the 80's when the boom of the same. In 1986, the World Labor Organization (ILO) reported the establishment of 176 zones in 47 countries. For 2006, this number increased to 3,500 zones in 130 countries".²

Despite its continued proliferation in the world, the results variable; for example, there are several Zones that function as catalysts in the processes of economic growth. This was particularly the case in Latin America, specifically in Central America, as well as in the economies of Asia, where we find the greatest success stories. On the contrary, there are areas that have had costly failures and have been criticized for failing to promote local economies, for social and labor reasons.

I. The Development of the Relationship between Mexico and China and Chinese Investment in Mexico

A. The relationship between Mexico and China

On February 14, 1972, diplomatic relations were established between the People's Republic of China and the United Mexican States. With the government of President Luis Echeverría Álvarez, a strong interest in the China and Mexico bond emerged, starting different projects to improve the relationship, such as academic programs, where students from the People's Republic of China were taught Spanish, which prepared A total of 151 students during the years 1974 to 1987.³

By 1995, during the administration of President Ernesto Zedillo, the Mexico-China relationship was very promising, since investment in China was a matter identified in the National Development Plan 1995-2000, which stated that: "In Asia Pacific, we will take full advantage of Mexico's membership of the region's main economic forums, such as APEC, to promote trade, investment and financial relations with its member countries, including some of the most dynamic economies Of the world and whose international role will be growing in

¹ <http://www.revistacomercioexterior.com/articulo.php?id=115&t=las-zonas-economicas-especiales>

² Centro de Estudios de las Finanzas Públicas. "Zonas Económicas Especiales, aspectos relevantes de la Iniciativa Aprobada", Palacio Legislativo de San Lázaro, mayo, 2016

³ VEY-DABBAH, Simón. China, la nueva fábrica del mundo, Grupo Editorial ISEF, México, 2003, pág. 230.

the future. We will also seek to establish closer ties with the People's Republic of China to multiply opportunities for trade with that nation".⁴

The Chinese authorities were grateful to Mexico for the solidarity that our country has long provided for the unification of their territories, as well as support for non-interference by other countries in matters of Chinese domestic politics.

On that occasion the Sino-Max-Textil project was signed, between the company Sinaloense Copel, S.S. And Fortune Co. of Shanghai, this agreement arose from the Chinese company's interest in importing cotton from Sinaloa.

Chinese President Juang Zenn visited Mexico in gratitude for Zedillo's assistance to China and on that visit Zenn expressed openly that there was a strong interest in the relationship between these two countries, as he wanted to enter the Central American market and Mexico could To open the doors to them in this region while China would help Mexico in its investment in Taiwan.

In the legislative order, the Senate of the Republic, by initiative, constituted a parliamentary group denominated "Group of Friendship Mexico-China" whose objective is the maintenance of an organization of seminars and fairs, during the exchange Legislative publications and other areas of interest.⁵

Though, there is a big disadvantage in the Mexico-China relationship and is that despite the good will that these two countries have shown to have a helping relationship and economic growth, China is a great competitor of Mexico in two sectors: In foreign investment and the main markets of the world.

Despite this, China has its eyes on our country, because Mexico has great influence in the Central American market that China wants to enter as soon as possible.

China, on the other hand, is working very closely and interested maintains a diplomatic corps in Mexico that collaborates in the embassy of China in Mexico that supports the Mexican academic institutions that are interested in the study of its country.

However, after the election results in the United States, Mexico's states are turning to Asia and beyond as some U.S. companies put investment plans on hold south of the border following President Donald Trump's calls to bring jobs back home.

A delegation of three Mexican state leaders, headed by the National Confederation of Governors (Conago), traveled to China this week to meet with business leaders and discuss investment opportunities.

Conago is developing an agenda with China's provinces to build investment projects in Mexico.

B. Chinese Investment in Mexico

In 2012, the relations between China and Mexico had entered a new period and reached a new historical level, after Mexican President Peña Nieto, who is from the Institutional Revolutionary Party, took office, and with the efforts made by both nations. Frequent visits and exchange of talks in multilateral and bilateral forums of the top leaders of both countries have been conducive to deepening the relations of these States. However, judging by the performance of the development of bilateral relations during the period, it is evident that there are still some areas that need to be improved. Therefore, it is not only necessary to evaluate the development of bilateral relations in the last three years; it is also urgent for both sides to maintain good political relations and to promote economic cooperation during the rest of President Peña Nieto's term.

⁴ National Development Plan, 1995-2000, <http://uninet.mty.itesm.mx/legis-demo/progs/pnd.htm#T1-C3-S3>

⁵ The friendship groups of the Legislative Power consist of deputies or senators from various parliamentary factions choose a country of their interest in order to maintain a close link to strengthen Mexico's relations with that nation or, if applicable, simple legislative cooperation.

So, what Mexico should consider is how to lay a solid foundation for bilateral relations to be good in the long run. Also, given the global and private economic situation of China and Mexico, there is a good opportunity for the two countries to achieve solid economic cooperation, with full use of existing mechanisms and measures at the regional and bilateral levels.

Economically, China remains the second largest trading partner of Mexico, while Mexico is China's second largest trading partner in Latin America and the Caribbean. Mexico is an important destination for China's FDI outflows. Unlike the declining volume of trade between China and the Latin American region in 2015, the trade volume between China and Mexico has continued to grow.

However, being the second largest economy in Latin America and a major destination for China's FDI outflows, Mexico attracted only 1.33% of China's investment in the region in 2014, and China's total outflow of investment to Mexico was 540 millions of US dollars by the end of 2014, which is much lower than in other countries in South America, such as Brazil, Venezuela, and Argentina.⁶

In general, relations between China and Mexico have developed smoothly over the past three years. However, so far the lack of success in economic cooperation in larger projects, particularly on those between China and other Latin American countries (e.g., Brazil and Argentina), indicates that there is still a large space for the cooperation. Being two large regional and even global countries, China and Mexico should maintain closer relations in general.

C. Foreign-related investment in Mexico

Mexico has become one of the most attractive countries for foreign direct investment due to all the positive characteristics that the country has; and on the other hand, also benefits the economy of the country by the inflow of investment flows.

First, its geographical location, since Mexico is located next to the 1st. World economy of the moment, which interests investors by making the negotiations with the United States more accessible, as well as having the advantage of being able to provide "just in time" to this country and therefore have the possibility to do more And better economic transactions with it.

Also, Mexico has a wide variety of natural resources, land, and climates conducive to the promotion of all types of industries, counting on materials such as petroleum, minerals, agricultural products, etc. They make cheaper the cost of raw materials for the production of all kinds of articles. Moreover, it also has resources that help to promote the tourism industry such as archaeological zones, beaches, mountains, jungle, desert, etc.

On the other hand, it is also interesting the fact that the labor of which is counted in our country is at a lower cost than in most developed countries. It should be mentioned that this workforce is young and relatively skilled, which makes production costs smaller and more competitive. It also has a favorable working environment, since in the last decade Mexico was considered the best destination for the placement of foreign capital in this area since, of the 500 main companies in Latin America, most have established their operations there.

Mexico, at the same time, benefits from having a considerable number of free trade agreements, which ensure preferential access to the markets of North America, the European Union, the countries of the European Free Trade Association, Israel and Ten Countries of Latin America. It is worth mentioning the treaties that have been signed in Mexico with other countries for free trade with them. Among them are NAFTA (The United States and Canada), free trade with the Republics of Colombia, Costa Rica, Bolivia, Nicaragua, Chile, Israel, the

⁶ Dussel, Enrique. "La Relación México-China, Desafío y Propuestas para 2016-2018, UNAM, MexCham, 2016, pag. 6

Northern Triangle (Guatemala, Salvador, Honduras), The States of the European Union, Uruguay, and Japan. In these treaties, preferential tariff rates are negotiated for the importation of products from these countries.⁷

Mexico has signed agreements for the promotion and reciprocal protection of investments to provide security and legal protection to foreign investors with around twenty. The Mexican Government has promoted transparency in its actions, respect for the rule of law and law enforcement, resulting in a stable environment favorable to business.

On the other hand, it is also important to mention the advantages that Mexico obtains in admitting Foreign Direct Investment.

FDI is now considered a fundamental part of any open international economic system considered as a fundamental part of the country's development.

One of the main benefits that Mexico obtains in admitting Direct Investment from other countries is, above all, the technological, economic and knowledge spillover that enters the country, achieving with this a greater integration of international trade giving impetus to a more competitive business environment. The above tends to contribute to economic growth.

II. The Special Legal System Adopted for Protection of Foreign Investment in the Special Economic Zones in Mexico

According to the approved Law, EEZs are a geographical area determined in unitary or by sections, subject to a special regime, in which activities of manufacturing, agroindustry, processing, processing and storage of raw materials and inputs may be carried out; Innovation and scientific and technological development; As well as the provision of support services to these tasks, among other activities.

It is important to emphasize that the three government levels⁸ will participate in the development and implementation of the EEZs, for this purpose they will conclude Coordination Agreements, in which they will establish the obligation of the three orders for the establishment and development of the Zones. Likewise, the government, together with the opinion of the private and social sector, will create a program called: Development Program, which will seek to establish the policies and actions that will allow the establishment and operation of these zones. The Economic and Social Sectors, contributing to the balance and sustainability of the projects.

According to 1st article of the Federal Law on Special Economic Zones, its objective is to regulate the planning, establishment and operation of EEZs to promote sustainable economic growth that, for other purposes, reduces poverty, allows The provision of basic services and expand opportunities for healthy and productive lives in the regions of the country that have the greatest lags in social development, through the promotion of investment, productivity, competitiveness, employment and a better income distribution Among the population.⁹

A. Tax and economic benefits

⁷ B Cobacho, R Caballero, M González, J Molina. Planning federal public investment in Mexico using multiobjective decision making, The Journal of the Operational Research Society, Vol. 61, No. 9 (September 2010), pg. 1330

⁸ Similar to the federal government of the United States, the Mexican federal government has three branches: executive, legislative, and judicial. Through the system of separation of powers each of these branches has some authority to act on its own, some authority to regulate the other two branches, and has some of its own authority regulated by the other branches.

⁹ Mexican Federal Law on Special Economic Zones

The companies that are located in the EEZ will have a series of fiscal and economic benefits, which will be established in the Decree of creation. The benefits granted should encourage the generation of permanent jobs, and productive investments that promote economic development and the creation of infrastructure, such as:

- Will have preferential financing from development banks
- A special customs regime will be created that will be regulated by the Customs Law, which will seek to promote the development, operation, and operation of EEZs.
- They will have special tax treatment.

B. Single Window

Each EEZ will have a Single Window to simplify and expedite the necessary procedures to build, develop, operate and manage the Zone; Carry out productive economic activities of the same, or install and operate companies in the Influence Area.

The Single Window shall be established using a joint agreement issued by the Federal Commission for Regulatory Improvement, the competent agencies, and parastatal entities, as well as the federal entities and municipalities that have signed the Coordination Agreement. Said agreement shall be published in the Official Gazette of the Federation and the local means of official dissemination.

The Single Window shall not require documents previously issued by the competent authorities participating in that window, privileging the least number of procedures and possible time in the resolution of the procedures assigned to the window.¹⁰

C. Establishment and Operation of Special Economic Zones

Under Article 19, for the construction, development, administration and maintenance of a zone, permits or allocations will be required that will be granted by the SHCP and will be governed by the following:

- a) Permits: May be granted to mercantile companies constituted according to Mexican legislation up to 40 years, taking into account, at least the existing infrastructure; The amounts of investment required by the Integral Administrator for the fulfillment of the objectives, the existence of skilled labor and the long-term financial viability. These Permits shall be renewable for a further period, when the Integral Administrator has fulfilled the obligations established in the Permit, including the standards of the Associated Services;

Permits will not be given at the moment when the interested parties do not prove their solvency or capacities when they do not have ownership of the real estate necessary to establish and operate the Zone, or the requirements contained in the guidelines are not met.

- b) Allocation: It will be granted to parastatal entities of the Federal Public Administration, when the Federal Executive considers that it is the most viable to develop it, said allocation would be granted through the Declaration Decree of the Zone.

Permits and assignments shall be terminated by expiration of the term established or extension, by resignation of the permittee or revocation of the permit or assignment, liquidation, extinction or bankruptcy of the permittee, however, the conclusion of the permit does not exempt the Integral Administrator from compliance with the obligations contracted during the validity of the same. The permit holders must comply with the rules issued for

¹⁰ Idem

this purpose by the SHCP, which must contain the requirements, procedures, and criteria under which the permits will be granted.

c) Revocation: Permits and Allocations may be revoked to the Integral Administrator

D. Rights and Obligations of Investors

Those interested in carrying out economic activities in the Area must obtain authorization from the SHCP, according to the guidelines issued by it. However, as far as Investors are concerned, the Law establishes different obligations, among which are:¹¹

- Construct buildings and install machinery and equipment to carry out productive economic activities;
- To receive the fiscal benefits and to be subject to the customs regime of the Zone,
- Obtain authorizations, licenses, and permissions
- Pay the consideration for the use and lease of goods, as well as for the provision of associated services;
- Hire the national or foreign personnel required for the development of their functions.
- Provide the information and documentation requested by the SHCP to verify compliance with the obligations under its responsibility;

With the approval of the Federal Law of Special Economic Zones, it is intended to provide greater openness to the productivity of strategic territorial zones, creating new poles of development; With the aim of reducing regional development gaps and improving the quality of life of the population living in extreme poverty, through the creation of basic services such as education, health, well-paid jobs, training, infrastructure, among others.

It is important to emphasize that these Zones will not be equal to each other, since they will depend on the strategic natural resources and the connectivity with which they count each region, that is to say, they will be tailor made costumes for each region, with the purpose of potentializing economic and social development taking into account the strengths of each region.¹²

The strategy of creating EEZs through a Law and not using other legal figures is of great importance, since national and foreign investors will have legal certainty with their investments, and the Federal Executive will continue the necessary public policies to achieve the objective set through its implementation, transcending beyond the political cycles of the country.

The Law contains the structural and legal elements necessary for the determination, creation, operation, control, monitoring, the participation of different levels of government, society, and academics, as well as important aspects of transparency and accountability to society and a sanctioning scheme for all EEZ participants.

Another aspect that stands out from the Law are the review periods of the Development Program and the Master Plan of the Zone, which allows to carry out the necessary modifications to reach the proposed development, as the national and international economic activity evolves, depending on the productive vocation of each EEZ.

III. Challenges of Chinese Investment in Mexico and Its Special Economic Zones

¹¹ Special Economic Zones. Relevant Aspects of the Approved Law Initiative, Center for Public Finance Studies, Congress of Mexico, 2016, pg. 25

¹² Idem

Eight years from the start of the crisis, the world economy is in "a trap of low growth." The persistent deceleration in the pace of growth is affecting production capacity in the future. Trade and investment at the international level remain weak, which is limiting improvements in productivity and wages.

“The world growth from this year will be around 3%, has been particularly slow and is expected to register only a modest recovery over the next two years. Among OECD economies, growth is even weaker - slightly below 2%. In Latin America a contraction is expected between -0.9 and -1% in 2016 and a slight recovery of 1.5% in 2017.”¹³

2012

Faced with this difficult context, Mexico has shown relative solidity. The Bank of Mexico has raised rates several times this year to counter inflationary pressures stemming from peso depreciation and to keep anchor inflation expectations. "Mexico's GDP growth is expected to reach 2% in 2016 - slightly above the OECD average - and increase in 2017 and 2018 to exceed 2.5%”.¹⁴

This last situation has been particularly relevant in the South of the country, where the three most behind regarding economic development and social welfare are located. "In 1990, the average gross domestic product (GDP) per capita of these states accounted for only 52.7% of per capita income nationwide. Over the next twenty years, the situation in this region continued to deteriorate, as this proportion reached 46.2% in 2010. At the same time, the incidence of property poverty increased from 71.8% to 72.2%”.¹⁵

Based on the above, the establishment of EEZs in Mexico is part of an approach that seeks to boost the development of modern infrastructure and logistics in the region. These areas will have preferential financing from development banks, facilities for foreign trade and special tax treatment; In short, it offers regulations that help to attract companies and create quality jobs, generating conditions to develop the human capital of our country, particularly the backward regions.

In that sense, the objective of the program announced by the President will be to draw from the economic and social stagnation suffered by a large part of the population of Chiapas, Guerrero, and Oaxaca, who contribute 7% of national GDP, of the national population.¹⁶

Mexico's economic performance over the past 20 years has not lived up to its potential, compared to the dynamism of other emerging economies. If Mexico fails to raise its long-term growth rate substantially, it will take several generations to achieve convergence with the living standards of other OECD countries. Reforms to increase the quality of primary and secondary education, strengthening competition and improving the regulatory framework will be key elements in this regard, as they increase productivity potential and improve the investment environment.

Fortunately, there is progress in education, such as increased spending on school infrastructure, the introduction in 2008 of a centralized entrance examination to select new teachers, and the plan to link teachers' professional progression more closely with their performance. Also, the government has proposed a labor reform, which, if approved, could have a very positive impact on formal employment.

¹³ Remarks by the Secretary General of the OECD José Angel Gurría. "The economic prospects of Mexico in the international context", Tijuana, México, November, 2016

¹⁴ Idem

¹⁵ Initiative of the Federal Law of Special Economic Zones and article 9 of the General Law of National Property is added.

¹⁶ Ibidem

Furthermore, in the social context, it is important to point out that Mexico is going through social and political changes. It is necessary to take in consideration that in 2016, different elections were held in more than 30 countries around the world.

Mexico is not the exception to this adverse scenario, the Mexican economy is ranked number fourteen in the world, which since its entry into the GATT in 1986 has accumulated eleven free trade agreements that lead it to interact commercially with more than forty and five countries (with the addition of thirty-three agreements for the promotion and reciprocal protection of investments and nine partial scope agreements), but the result is not tangible despite having a large number of trade agreements. Has managed to grow at the level demanded by poverty levels.

According to World Bank estimates, global economic growth in a report released in January of this year, says that following the low levels registered last year after the crisis, by 2017 is forecast a 2.7% moderate acceleration in economic growth World, in a context where the obstacles to the activity of commodity exporters in emerging markets and developing economies diminish, while domestic demand between commodity importers in emerging countries remains strong and developing.

According to the World Bank's January World Economic Outlook, in advanced economies growth is expected to rebound to 1.8% by 2017.¹⁷ The forecasts indicate that the region will return in 2017 to positive growth, which will be 1.2%. Brazil is expected to grow at a rate of 0.5% thanks to the reduction of internal difficulties. The decline in investment in Mexico, due to political uncertainty in the United States, is expected to result in a moderate growth slowdown this year, at 1.8%. The recovery of fiscal consolidation and improved investment is expected to support growth in Argentina, which is expected to grow at a rate of 2.7% in 2017, while in the Bolivarian Republic of Venezuela, which continues to suffer from deep economic imbalances, It is expected that there will be a contraction of 4.3% this year. The forecast of growth in the Caribbean countries, of 3.1%, is considered stable in general terms.¹⁸

Derived that geopolitics reconfigures in an important way after the triumph of nationalists and populists in diverse latitudes of the world could also have an impact in Mexico. It is, therefore, necessary to take into consideration that two factors could limit the flow of productive investment for Mexico this year and the next: the result of the renegotiation of the North American Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA) and populism in the elections Presidential

"If investors are aware of an environment of uncertainty about the future of Mexico's government policies, there will undoubtedly be an effect on the flow of capital. Investors invariably take their resources to markets that give them certainty".¹⁹

A. Case of the Queretaro train

For Beijing, the US \$ 3,750 million projects for the construction of a 210-kilometer road to link Mexico City with Queretaro meant global recognition of Chinese railway technology.

The development of this high-speed rail industry has been one of the standards of the Asian giant in recent years. Moreover, now, for the first time, China would not only export parts of its systems, as it had in the past.

¹⁷ <http://www.bancomundial.org/es/news/press-release/2017/01/10/global-growth-edges-up-to-2-7-percent-despite-weak-investment>

¹⁸ Idem

¹⁹ Gregory Daco, chief economist for US of Oxford Economics. Press Conference, Mexico City, March, 2017

However, the disenchantment of the bullet train as the Hong Kong newspaper called it came a few days later. On Thursday, November 6, 2014, the Secretary of Communications and Transport (SCT) of Mexico, Gerardo Ruiz Esparza, announced that the decision of the tender for the construction of the Mexico-Querétaro fast train was without effect.

It was a decision that took China as a surprise to the people of Mexico, not only because of the huge amount of money involved but also because of China's ambition to export its high-speed technology. It should also be borne in mind that this was to be the first contract that China won abroad, which, it was supposed, would set a good precedent.

On Friday, after the announcement, CRCC fell 4.94% on the Shanghai Stock Exchange and 5.76% on the Hong Kong stock market, its biggest drop since July 2013.

Tian Yuan law firm in Beijing, which said that CRCC was considering possible legal action to seek compensation for losses caused by the abrupt decision of the Mexican government.²⁰

China made clear that its offer had complied with all regulations and that the contract had been revoked by "Mexican internal factors."

It was reported that the Chinese consortium had been the sole bidder for the ambitious Mexican project after 16 other companies had declined the call, including the main global competitors of CRCC: the German Siemens, the Canadian Bombardier, the French Alstom and the Japanese Mitsubishi.

Charges of opposition politicians arose that the supply platform had not been fair and that the three Mexican companies participating in the consortium led by CRCC had close ties to the government.

Based on the above analysis, it can be said that both China and Mexico should focus on important issues, while separating a little from the minor issues, at least during the development of bilateral relations, especially when dealing with accidents. The old Chinese saying "past, past" gives us good reason to look forward, as well as stimulate us to promote healthier bilateral relations today. Judging from the current situation of economic cooperation, it is much more important to act in the direction of deepening understanding and building trust between the two sides and with entrepreneurs, in particular through new and diverse cooperation projects that are successful in the short term, if this were possible. Today is the crucial time to reflect on how a solid foundation should be laid to encourage the sustained development of bilateral relations in the long term. Undoubtedly, relations between China and Mexico have a bright future, although it will inevitably be that during their development they also face some new difficulties.

B. Challenges Facing Chinese Investment

A major difference between Mexico and China is that the latter has a clear and long-term strategy on what to do with its main trading partners, in general, with the countries with which it has economic and diplomatic relations, which has meant good Part of its economic success by integrating the world economy in a big way.

Mexico, for its part, does not have a well-defined national strategy for its development within the next few years, and specifically, it does not have a clear strategy on its relationship with China. This is evidenced both in the National Development Plan 2013-2018 (PND, 2013) and in the sectoral program of foreign relations of the Mexican Chancery, which is a joint treatment of China with Japan and the so-called new countries of recent industrialization (NIC), A situation that seems incomprehensible.

²⁰ <http://cidac.org/eng/the-case-of-the-m/>

As explained above, the Asian giant accounts for a large percentage of Mexico's trade deficit with the world and with Asia-Pacific. Alternatively, if you want to see from another point of view, represent a great opportunity for the development of Mexico. However, the opportunity must be taken and laid the groundwork to exploit it in the best possible way. For this reason, the construction of a short- and medium-term work agenda for China is essential (Calvo, 2011: 9). By this possible agenda, Mexico may propose a new bilateral relationship with China where the benefits are effectively mutual and contributing to the achievement of the economic objectives of both countries, thus helping to rebalance the relationship for Mexico.

With a selective strategy, it is possible to establish clearly the purposes that are sought with the new existing bilateral relationship, and the economic and commercial actions to be followed to meet those objectives, with the firm intention of achieving the objectives of the Best Possible form

In summary, Mexico needs a strategy to ensure foreign investment regardless of political and social changes and a strategic industrial policy that promotes a new global industrial and commercial strategy, and does not leave aside the essential objectives for the new bilateral relationship, for the benefit of the wider interests of the country, the advantages offered by the economy More dynamic in the world, or to counteract the disadvantages that this economic power has brought to Mexico in recent years.

IV. Suggestions and Recommendations

The development of bilateral relations at present has to be realistic, as the challenges arising from trade between the two economies remain in force despite the decreasing trend in their intensity and frequency. It should also be borne in mind that, although the difference between the two countries regarding GDP per capita is decreasing, at the moment it is not convenient for either party to resort to the traditional scheme of signing a treaty Free trade as a way to strengthen bilateral relations.

On the Chinese side, economic policies have changed substantially; nowadays, greater emphasis is placed on the promotion of the domestic market and domestic consumption. In that context, the potential Mexican market would mean a small share of the country's total trade with the rest of the world. One fact that deserves some observations is that the valuation of international bilateral relations often uses as a parameter the subscription or not of a free trade agreement between two nations.

Most of the time this has happened in Mexico almost as a sole criterion, especially since the negotiations of the Free Trade Agreement with the United States and Canada and its subsequent signature and operation in 1994. Undoubtedly, the regulated bilateral trade exchanges by a treaty are central to the construction of relations between two countries, but they are not the only factor.

That is why the signing of a strategic and comprehensive partnership agreement between China and Mexico shows a tone different from that accustomed in modern history and marks the beginning of a new stage. Under this scheme, a prosperous and mutually beneficial bilateral relationship can be established. Surely during this process will appear challenges, obstacles, unpleasant eventualities; however, if both nations adhere to the principles of mutual respect, if they maintain a permanent dialogue, if they have a realistic and intelligent vision especially in the long term, one can trust that the challenges can be overcome, and mutual understanding will be more efficient.

Today, it seems urgent and necessary to establish a clear route to concrete bilateral economic relations. To achieve this, we could make full use of existing mechanisms at the multinational, regional and binational levels.

There are reasons for both countries to solve the difficulties since China and Mexico have more favorable conditions than before to develop bilateral relations.

In addition to good political relations, as members of organizations such as the G-20, APEC and others, policymakers in both nations are more likely to meet and talk.

The two countries' structural economic reforms, as well as China's recently implemented strategies, including Industrial Production Capacity, also provide a new opportunity for the development of China-Mexico relations.

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